

Examining the Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction for a Restaurant – A Multi Regression Approach

Ayesha Khan¹, Muhammad Abdullah Idrees², Munazza Rahim Hanafi³, Sehrish Qasim Ali⁴

Abstract

This study observed the direct impact of food quality, service quality, price and ambiance on the customer satisfaction, in the Karachi Restaurant segment. This research is based upon the individuals of Karachi, that has the aggregate population of around 2.2 Million, so the sample size for the population of Karachi is 385 participants, that means that the data has to be gathered through this size by which the prove the research. It is based upon the Positivism research philosophy because in the following research quantitative data and assumptions. The Research Design is related with the Quantitative Research. Non-probability, the convenience sampling has been used. The regression analysis is also supposed to be used to evaluate the outcomes of the research. Findings of the study informs that restaurants should work on price as compare to other variables because customers are getting satisfied from the service and quality of food but not from the price they are offering. If we talk about the respondents, so in this study we have collected the data from different culture consumers from all over the population of Karachi and have tested the data.

Keywords: Customer Satisfaction, Service Quality, Food Quality, Price, Ambiance

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

As the world is adapting changes rapidly, so does the numerous industries are getting emerged or evolved. There is a huge number of Industries that are playing an important role in the world, but we are being considerate towards the Restaurant Industry respectively. In the recent times, it has been observed that people are getting conscious about the food that is being offered to them at different Restaurants. A number of previous studies have highlighted the importance of two factors that are Quality of food and Quality of service in the Restaurant Industry, acclaiming that it is quality perception the customer keeps in mind, has a massive effect on their satisfaction level along with the word of mouth. It has been observed that a quality service by the employees engenders a greater level of customer satisfaction, which positively affects the word of mouth of that specific Restaurant.

In addition, the prior studies have acknowledged atmospheric conditions as an additional significant part of the practices of having meal and states that atmospheric conditions affect the sentiments and assumptions related to the quality of service and quality of food (Wall, 2007; Senturk & Ali, 2022; Sulehri et al., 2022). Before availing any service, the first thing that impacts customer satisfaction is the atmospheric conditions, because at the time she/he arrives at the restaurant, first thing he experiences is the atmosphere of the restaurant. Therefore, the sentiments that are created by the observation of the atmospheric conditions can deeply affect the customer's response to the other two factors of quality that are services and food (Zeithaml, 1993; Shahid & Ali, 2015).

The representation of the Restaurant is known as a significant factor of the customer satisfaction, and thus it is a keystone of the accomplishment of the excellent dining restaurants. (Downs. E, 1984), mentioned the connection between the restaurant accomplishment and the usefulness of its representation management. An excellent dining restaurant, thus, ought to concentrate on its representation by means of augmented advancements and perfection in furnishings, environment and interior decor to draw attention of customers and to distinguish itself from its opponent restaurants.

Luckily for the excellent dining Restaurants, The National Restaurant Association (NRA) has stated that the quality of service is as essential as the quality of food. Furthermore, it has stated that the place and the environment are equally essential that proposes that the consumers are ready to pass through additional routes to support those Restaurants that are giving excellent quality in food as well as in the service in the most affordable prices. The study of (NRA) has also proposed that around 25 % of the total customers are classified as "audacious" and are excited for trying innovative menus. Most of the customers are aged between 30-60 years, those are literate and are mostly energetic Restaurant consumers. An excessive food menu and an exceptional atmosphere can different an excellent dining Restaurant from its competitors. The Restaurant's infrastructure, designing, background and the locality can be used productively to influence consumers in a soaked market and in opposition to stronger rivalry. The diners, who earn higher income, get attached to the excellent dining or mesmerizing Restaurants because they are conscious about their representation and sense that offer communal worth for them. It is recognized as an involvement to their societal standing for them (Elva, 1993).

1.2. Research Problem

We are living in the era, where food is valued at a higher rate, and the customers get easily dissatisfied, if they are not given the proper treatment in the Restaurants. While choosing the quality of food in the Restaurant, customers get very sensitive and a single mismanagement in any factor can make your customer disloyal. The reason of this study is to examine, differentiate and estimate the factors of the customer's satisfaction in the fast-food industry.

¹Bahria University, Karachi, Pakistan

²Corresponding Author: Denning Business School, Karachi, Pakistan, Email: m.abdullahidrees91@gmail.com

³Indus University, Karachi, Pakistan

⁴Bahria University, Karachi, Pakistan

1.3. Limitations

As there are limitations in each research, similarly there are limitations in this study as well, that are as follows: Firstly, Limitations occurred while distributing the questionnaire because we have to wait for customer to finish their meal and fill the questionnaire afterwards. Secondly, Due to the factors like quality of food and service, the survey had to take place in renowned Restaurants for accurate results (Wu & Liang, 2009). There might be disparity because of the reality that the diners are mostly teachers and students and they might have diverse level of satisfaction than the other dining customer divisions (Elva, 1993).

2. Literature Review

In the prior researches about the restaurant industry, it is studied that customer satisfaction is the important factor, on which the restaurants image and ownership is relying upon. More, there are in depth variables which effects the customer satisfaction and make it positive image and negative image both, but the most studied elements are: quality of food, quality of service, price and the atmospheric condition and there are many more which impacts customer satisfaction in indirect ways.

Further, it is discussed that it is necessary for the management of the restaurant to be more focused on the loyalty of the consumer, as the customer is everything for the restaurant and they need to fulfill their needs for the future success of the restaurant (Surlemont, 2005).

2.1. Theoretical Background

Moreover, all the services are original with slight or null tangible substitute goods. In restaurant industry the subsidizing section is service which is flimsy and assorted, whereas the formation and consumption of the good might not be distributed. And it is examined that mostly the diners look and desire for the number of places and foods for their regular and selects the restaurants so they can go and have their meal with different variety on rotary basis (Neal, 1999). So, there is a great influence of the factors like: Food Quality, Service Quality, Price and Ambiance on the Satisfaction level of the customer. Food Quality influences the taste buds of the customer, and whenever he/she wants to eat the same food, he/she always remembers the same Restaurant where he has tasted the delicious food. Service Quality plays a vital part role in making the customer to have a positive word of mouth afterwards, because if for once the service quality gets even average the customer won't be any more satisfied with it nor he will recommend the same Restaurant to someone else.

2.2. Conceptual Framework

2.2.1. Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction as dependent variables has been reviewed by many scholars and researchers in their literatures by focusing on the variables that measure customer satisfaction (Oliver, 1997). In his literature, defines customer satisfaction as a customer's situation on the time of post purchase decision. Oliver states that a decision is made when the experience of buying a good is equivalent to or exceeds customer gratification through factors including competitive pricing, quality of food, good value, quick service, courteous employees and other.

(Reuland, 1985) Moreover defines customer experience comprising of three traits i.e., materialism, behavior of employees, and atmosphere which can influence satisfaction positively or negatively.

However, Berry (2002) in their research findings affirmed three aspects which has a relative effect on the consideration of service experience namely; technical quality, environment tangibles, and lastly the behavior of employees in the restaurant service. In conclusion to the above statements taken in from past researches, the current study limits its variables with the aim of customer satisfaction measurements which are quality of food, price competitiveness and atmosphere of the restaurant.

Customer satisfaction is a primary role in hotel business, one satisfied customer can bring a chain of continuous satisfied customers within the business, leading to customer loyalty (Yi, 1990), in addition, and unsatisfied customers may take away existing customers from the business. In this effect, service companies of today have increased by offering considerable benefits in order to generate customer satisfaction and exceeding customer expectations.

Poor customer service and failure to provide first-rate experience can place a negative side effect on all the business areas and no such restaurant likes being subject to anger from displeased customers. Without sufficient strategies in place to deal with customer's complaint, customers are likely to feel dissatisfied with a service restaurant. The most crucial part to assess customer satisfaction is tracking customer satisfaction through assessment procedure (Back, 2005). This is the reason many restaurant owners of today's are making effective adjustments like customer service assessments to note the course of customers that deals with testing of customer interaction, product knowledge, attitude and behavior of customer. The assessment procedure by many scholars has been thought as the most effective tools to evaluate customer service skills (Ryu, Han, & Kim, 2008).

2.2.2. Service Quality

In accordance with the studies, it is being examined that the service quality is appeared to be an important factor in creating CS. Most of the times, the quality of service is observed through two views, the one is the customer's logical evaluation by the service providers (Taylor, 1994), and the second one is multi-dimensional concept that is made from the assessment of service quality being provided (Parasuraman A. Z., 1988). If the service quality can be further discussed, it is discussed as the decision from the complete experience of the customer, that they have been served; it directly influences their level of satisfaction to either re-visit or to have a positive or negative word of mouth (Zeithaml V. , 1988).

It has been observed that from the view of decision and the perspective of research the service quality has an influence of mainly two things, the one is the consuming affect in which the experience is counted it and the second one is the buying behavior of the customer that affects the re-visit or the re-purchase for the certain objective or place (Holbrook, 1995). In the buying behavior the satisfaction affects the belief of approval and disconfirmation. Therefore, this is showing that the buying behavior affects the relationship between the customer satisfaction and service quality (Anderson, 1994)(Bitner, 1994). The findings and the studies show that services in the Restaurant are of many types that directly impacts the satisfaction level of the customer, if the better quality is provided by the Restaurant, the more satisfied customer will be (Chow, 2007). Therefore, we construct the hypothesis as:

H1: Service quality has a positive effect on Customer Satisfaction.

2.2.3. Food Quality

Among the significant factors of the Restaurant Industry, the quality of food is the most important (Namkung, 2007). In the recent times, the researcher observed the impact of food quality on CS and behavioral intention and found out a positive relationship between the food quality and customer satisfaction. The food quality has been examined through different characteristics. In addition, (Sulek, 2004) declared that three common food characteristics decide the quality of food that are: safety, demand and nutritional acceptability. In these characteristics, demand contains numerous objects, such as flavor, appearance, consistency, color, warmth, and size of the place.

Sulek and Hensley (2004) examined the importance of food, atmospheric conditions and quality of service in Restaurants and originated that the quality of food is the most significant characteristic affecting the satisfaction of the diner and thus the one and only characteristic that can foresee the future intention of the diner. It has been shown by the research that the quality of the good is frequently a significant characteristic affecting the loyalty of the diners/customers in the consideration of selecting the Restaurant (Clark, 1999). Hence, the Hypothesis is derived as:

H2: Food Quality has a positive effect on Customer Satisfaction.

2.2.4. Price

As it is being discussing about the attributes that are impacting on customer satisfaction, here the variable price also plays a vital role in, influencing the satisfaction of customer in the industry of restaurant. Moreover, primary researches tell us that integrity in price is a mental factor as a response from customer towards price (Kim, 2006). (Ranaweera, 2003) researched that reasonable pricing have a positive effect on customer satisfaction and maintaining customers toward restaurant, as it is natural mindset of human to stick with the restaurant which offers good quality food in a good atmosphere with reasonable price, hence this cycle will make the customer loyal and will also recommend to others which will bring more customers to the restaurant and the percentage of profit also

increases. Furthermore, the research also shows the other side of the effect that as we are studying on price variable, in every business prices are set according to the required profit margin in accordance with the product and none businesses run on loss or on breakeven point, but in the industry of restaurants it is also seen that the certain restaurant is not providing that type of ambiance and quality food as they have set the prices for their menu, and from here the negative effects start in satisfying consumers. In the previous researches they have examined that justice in price factor has a direct impact on their customers as well as on the quality of the restaurant (Meng & Elliott, 2008).

According to the different researches we get to know that most of the times prices are not according to the restaurant quality, like if the customer sees that prices are high so they expect to get pampered very well and if the overall services are not according to that it decreases the satisfaction level plus these customers are not coming back again and also not recommending to any others which will result the loss in all means. But as we talk about the human psychology it is also examined that if the customer sees that certain restaurant is offering food in a low budget so is their food quality be good or is their food is healthy and many questions raises as today's generation are very health conscious and they do not like to neglect on food quality over price (Andaleeb & Conway, 2006). On concluding about the variable price all the above researches prove that pricing is playing a significant role in restaurant industry and is directly impacting customer satisfaction in all aspects, as they are paying a hefty amount against food so they expect to be that great quality of food in return (Rehman, Akhtar, Hafeez, Ghafoor, & Sabir, 2014). Hence, the derived hypothesis which is as:

H3: Price has the Positive effect on Customer Satisfaction.

2.2.5. Ambiance

Further on moving to the next factor that is ambiance of the restaurant which is also a vital variable in satisfying customer and affecting it positively by making them loyal to the restaurant. These are the factors which a customer examines the environment of the restaurant like how the employees are suited up, the way they are talking, serving the customers and how well the infrastructure of restaurant is and in what way they have decorated and how well they are accommodating the customers, and all these together influences the customer plus the environment of the restaurant.

A customer also perceives the atmosphere of the restaurant by its surrounding area. If we talk about fine dining so it is always assumed that fine dine ambiance is good, comforting and decorative which inspires the satisfaction level more and encourage the customer to visit again. On the other side, in previous studies it's researched that the environment of the restaurant plays a part of marketing as well. Like a customer visits a place and he is completely satisfied with everything by all the services so he will surely visit again plus he will spread a word of mouth in his circle and it is studied that word of mouth is one of the marketing strategies and it's likely to have many customers because of this reason. Hence, it is also researched that when people are starting their business in restaurant industry they mainly focus on environment, hygiene and the quality of food (Liu & Jang, 2009).

Therefore, the hypothesis is presented as:

H4: Ambiance has a Positive effect of Customer Satisfaction.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Research Design and Approach

The research design used in this research is quantitative research and the method of it is cause and effect between the variables.

3.2. Data Collection Method

The data is collected through primary source with the help of questionnaire. The questionnaire is consist of close-ended questions.

3.3. Research Philosophy

The following study is based upon the Positivism because in the following research quantitative data and assumptions are used to analyze the outcome that is scientifically established and are mathematically confirmed (Schuilenburg, 2008).

3.4. Sampling Size

To find a sample size particular calculator is being used in this research that is Rao soft calculator which helps in finding a sample size of the research. The following research is based upon the individuals of Karachi, that has the aggregate population of around 2.2 Million, so the sample size for the population of Karachi is 385 participants, that means that the data has to be gathered through this size by which to prove the research.

3.5. Sampling Techniques

In the following research the non-probability, the convenience sampling has been used.

3.6. Statistical Tool

The regression analysis is supposed to be used to evaluate the outcomes of the research.

4. Finding and Analysis:

4.1. Descriptive Analysis

To evaluate the uni-variate of the items we examine it with the help of Skewness and Kurtosis analysis. Table 1 represents the descriptive statistics.

Table 1

	Mean	Std. Dev	Skewness	Kurtosis
Food Quality	4.0344	.63038	-1.030	1.774
Price	3.3776	.79280	.067	-.466
Ambience	3.9026	.73538	-.439	-.345
Service Quality	3.8738	.74223	-.691	.709
Customer Satisfaction	3.7834	.64781	-.540	.765

The above Table 1, Food Quality ($m=4.03$, $SD=.6303$) has the greatest Skewness i.e. (-1.030) that goes after by Service Quality ($m=3.87$, $SD=.742$), Customer Satisfaction ($m=3.78$, $SD=.647$), Ambience ($m=3.90$, $SD=.735$), Price ($m=3.37$, $SD=.79$) having the lowest skewness i.e. (.067).

On the other side, the Food Quality ($m=4.0344$, $SD=.63038$) has the highest kurtosis i.e. (1.774), and the Ambience ($m=3.9026$, $SD=.73538$) has the lowest kurtosis i.e. (-.345).

According to the results, it can be seen that the values of skewness & kurtosis are in the ideal range, it is hence proved that the constructs do not disturb the state of univariate normality.

4.2. Reliability Analysis

Internal consistency of all the constructs was analyzed with the help of Cronbach's alpha. For that the results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2

	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha based Standardized	Mean	Std. Dev
Food Quality	.800	.805	4.0344	.63038
Price	.822	.821	3.3776	.79280
Ambience	.792	.804	3.9026	.73538
Service Quality	.890	.891	3.8738	.74223
Customer Satisfaction	.828	.843	3.7834	.64781

In addition, Table 2, shows that the Service Quality ($\alpha=.890$, $m=3.8738$, $SD=.74223$) has the greatest reliability, and is followed by Customer Satisfaction ($\alpha=.828$, $m=3.7834$, $SD=.64781$), Price ($\alpha=.822$, $m=3.3776$, $SD=.79280$), Food Quality ($\alpha=.800$, $m=4.0344$, $SD=.63038$), Ambience ($\alpha=.792$, $m=3.9026$, $SD=.73538$) has the lowest reliability.

All the tested values of Cronbach's alpha are greater than the value (0.60) that endorses the internal uniformity of the constructs.

4.3. Correlation

To examine the multi-collinearity, distinctiveness of the adapted constructs bi-variate correlation analysis is tested. The summarized results are shown in the Table 3.

Table 3

	Food Quality	Price	Ambience	Service Quality	Customer Satisfaction
Food Quality	1				
Price	.249	1			
Ambience	.546	.186	1		
Service Quality	.634	.224	.590	1	
Customer Satisfaction	.609	.289	.700	.702	1

Table 3 shows the greatest correlation is ($r=.702$) is linking between customer satisfaction and service quality. While on the other hand, the lowest correlation ($r=.186$) that is between ambience and price. As it can be seen that all variables except Price are ranged between 0.30-0.90, that means it has been established that the constructs have no problem with the multi-collinearity and all the variables are distinctive whereas, the variable Price has no value that is ranging between 0.30 to 0.90, that means it has a weak relationship with the other variable, thus it is not distinctive.

4.4. Multiple Regression

The effect of all independent constructs on dependent construct is examined through multiple regressions. Tables show the summarized result.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.798	.637	.633	.39116		
Anova						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	101.006	4	25.251	165.038	.000
	Residual	57.529	376	.153		
	Total	158.535	380			
Coefficients						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.	
	Constant	.368	.147		2.495	.013
	Food Quality	.148	.043	.144	3.417	.001
	Price	.083	.026	.101	3.134	.002
	Ambience	.343	.035	.390	9.754	.000
	Service Quality	.311	.038	.356	8.210	.000

Customer satisfaction as a dependent variable, R-square = .637 and adjusted R-square = .633, F= (4, 376) = 165.038, p= 0 < 0.05.

The outcome of the regression shows that (Food quality, Price, Ambience and Service quality) outlines 63.7% of the variance, where F= (4, 376) = 165.038, p= 0 < 0.05. It is also seen that ambience ($\beta = .390$, p= < 0.05) is vitally effecting on customer satisfaction followed by service quality ($\beta = .356$, p= < 0.05), food quality ($\beta = .144$, p= < 0.05), price ($\beta = .101$, p= < 0.05). Hence, the proven model is explaining the impact on customer satisfaction which is resilient from the following regression equation.

4.5. Simple Regression

Hypothesis 1: Food Quality and Customer Satisfaction

The hypothesis of food quality is positively effecting on customer satisfaction which is examined through simple regression test. Tables show the analysis.

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.609	.371	.370	.51301		
Anova						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	59.216	1	59.216	225.002	.000
	Residual	100.272	381	.263		
	Total	159.488	382			
Coefficients						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	
	Constant	1.268	.170		7.460	.000
	Food Quality	.625	.042	.609	15.000	.000

The above table shows that Food quality has 37.1% of variance on customer satisfaction with (r-square = .371, F (1, 381) = 225.002, p= < 0.05). Therefore, food quality has positive effect on customer satisfaction.

Hypothesis 2: Price and Customer Satisfaction

Price is positively impacting on the customer satisfaction which hypothesis is tested by simple regression. The analysis of this hypothesis is presented in Tables.

Table 6: Model Summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.289	.083	.081	.62179		
Anova						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.433	1	13.433	34.745	.000
	Residual	147.689	382	.387		
	Total	161.122	383			
Coefficients						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Constant	2.986	.139			21.477	.000
Price	.236	.040	.289		5.895	.000

The result demonstrates that Price has 8.3% variance on customer satisfaction on (r-square = .083, F (1, 382) = 34.745, $p < 0.05$). So, it is proven that price have positive impact on customer satisfaction.

Hypothesis 3: Ambience and Customer Satisfaction

Hypothesis of ambience effecting positively on customer satisfaction is verified through simple regression. The result of hypothesis is shown in Tables.

Table 7: Model Summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.700	.490	.489	.46242		
Anova						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	78.527	1	78.527	367.236	.000
	Residual	81.684	382	.214		
	Total	160.211	383			
Coefficients						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Constant	1.378	.128			10.799	.000
Ambience	.616	.032	.700		19.163	.000

The table shows the result that Ambience has 49% of variance with customer satisfaction on (r-square = .490, F (1, 382) = 367.236, $p < 0.05$). Hence, it is verified that ambience is positively effecting on customer satisfaction.

Hypothesis 4: Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

The variable Service quality is positively impacting on customer satisfaction and the hypothesis is examined by simple regression which results are shown in Tables.

Table 8: Model Summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.702	.493	.492	.46167

Anova						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	79.515	1	79.515	373.062	.000
	Residual	81.633	383	.213		
	Total	161.148	384			

Coefficients					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	1.408	.125		11.250	.000
Service Quality	.613	.032	.702	19.315	.000

The construct Service quality has 49.3% of variance on customer satisfaction with (r-square = .493, $F(1, 383) = 373.062$, $p < 0.05$). So, the construct service quality is proving that its hypothesis is confirmed that it is effecting positively on customer satisfaction.

5. Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1. Discussion

This study observed the direct impact of food quality, service quality, price and ambiance on the customer satisfaction, in the Karachi Restaurant segment. As an aggregate this study has established the fact that customers' views of quality (food as well the service) have a great influence upon the customer satisfaction. This study has also evolved that the impact of the cultural restaurants' service and the quality of food on the satisfaction can be differentiated dependent upon how the ambiance of the place has been observed. Though, the following study has a bit different point of view in terms of the ambiance and there is an emergence of another factor that is price, and that the ambiance, quality (food & service) as well as the price keeps the customer motivated or de-motivated towards the restaurant. The following study explains the role of service and food quality as well as of the ambiance that how the customer gets fascinate with the better environment and will the pleased behavior of the personnel's there and how deliberately the food quality satisfies the customer and yet again the ambiance of the place makes the things nicer for the customer. The findings of the study suggest that the customer gets highly influenced firstly by the ambiance of the place and secondly by the attitude of the employees treating them, before availing any food service, and price really does not affect the perception of the customer as the customer has overall impression of all the restaurants whether they are the Five-Star Hotel or the Three-Star Hotel. The service quality and the ambiance of the place thus play the most significant role in the level of satisfaction among customers. The following study has the supervisory implications too. All these findings propose that irrespective of the ambiance of the Restaurant, assessing the quality food as well as the service is also an important factor to bring the satisfaction of the customer. Provision of better quality of service as well as the food can immediately enhance the level of satisfaction of the customers with a low awareness of the ambiance. Basically, the vendors of the small Restaurants in Karachi, whose economic resources are restricted should be paying more attention towards the reliability and promptness of better service and the better-quality food, that may include the tasty food, a greater variety in menu, along with the healthy options, rather than investing upon the ambiance of the place. The following resulted proposed that the better service and food excellence can be effectual for persuading the higher level of satisfaction among the customers with the comparatively little perception of the ambiance.

5.2. Conclusion

Results of the existing research gives a point of view regarding understanding the impact of quality that a restaurant is providing including their services, atmosphere, food quality and price on customer satisfaction. Different from the prior study in which environment issues are measured as a part of service quality. Whereas, in this study we got to know that there are several parts of quality such as food quality, service quality and atmosphere which leads to customer satisfaction. Findings of the study informs that restaurants should work on price as compare to other variables because customers are getting satisfied from the service and quality of food but not from the price they are offering. If we talk about the respondents, so in this study we have collected the data from different culture consumers from all over the population of Karachi and have tested the data.

Thus, for the future study this can be good though many of them have not visited fine dining but they are at least familiar with the name, quality and environment of the restaurant and have perception in their mind. To get the better results in future it is need to identify the familiarity level of customer with that restaurant so that we can get more good results regarding the constructs. Survey questions should be in a manner that would affect their memories and the time period should also be noted that when they last had the fine dining and when this survey

is taking place so it shows us who accurate the results can be. Moreover, the study is based on casual-dining Pakistani restaurants.

5.3. Recommendations

Future researchers can focus on customer's characteristics, their perception and customer loyalty and how it affects their satisfaction for a dining experience in a restaurant as the factors used in this research are of restaurants perspective, however, consumer's perspective also affects customer satisfaction to a great extent which can be studied for future research. Along with the above mentioned factors, there is one more factor that needs to be researched and that is also the part of the following research that is Price. The factor Price had the low-level relationship with each variable, which shows that the researchers and the owners of the Restaurant need to focus on the Price too, as it is the most influential factor that can set the parameters for satisfaction of the customers.

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